

Quantitative Analysis of User Activity on the Ficbook Platform

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1. Introduction

Fanfiction in the Russian-language segment of the internet remains a mass phenomenon, but one that is still weakly studied empirically. Despite the existence of a considerable number of publications on the subject, most of them are theoretical or descriptive and do not rely on quantitative data. At the same time, since the 2010s, Ficbook has functioned as the largest Russian-language platform for amateur literature and as an independent digital ecosystem combining the functions of a literary platform, a social network, a space for self-realization, and an environment for collective critique. According to Semrush, in late 2025 the monthly traffic of ficbook.net exceeded 40 million visits, which confirms the scale of user activity on the platform. Ficbook is a place where not only texts are produced, but also stable mechanisms of interaction between authors and readers: comments, internal hierarchies of authority, quality norms, and practices of self-reflection.

Despite the high level of user activity on Ficbook, quantitative studies of its internal structure and reader behavior remain few. One of the largest works in this field is the study by P. I. Maksimenko, in which web scraping was used to create an electronic database of 136,257 completed texts and metadata published on Ficbook between 2009 and 2013. This made it possible to conduct a corpus analysis of Russian-language fanfiction and identify stable patterns in the distribution of works by fandom, genre, rating, and category/direction. A significant contribution to the study of fanfiction audiences was made by M. A. Kashina and A. A. Pedchenko, who examine fanfiction as a form of new social media within the framework of convergence culture. Based on an online survey of 1,007 respondents, the authors characterized the readership of the Russian-language fanfiction community and identified its main reading motivations, genre preferences, and the functions of fanfiction as a space for communication, leisure, and immediate feedback. At the same time, the internal structure of Ficbook, the dynamics of completion for large works, the distribution of reader engagement, and changes in user activity after the platform was blocked by Roskomnadzor remain insufficiently studied.

After Ficbook was blocked by Roskomnadzor on July 14, 2024, not only the conditions of access to the platform changed, but also the environment in which the author community exists. Reduced accessibility of the resource, audience migration, and changes in reading and publication habits could affect both the intensity of feedback and authors' ability to bring large works to completion. At the same time, a direct comparison of overall activity is difficult: some works started after the block have not yet had enough time to go through the full cycle of publication, completion, and accumulation of reader response.

For this reason, the study does not attempt to prove an absolute decline in activity. Instead, it focuses on analyzing changes in the structure of completed maxi works, the characteristics of reader engagement, and the relationship between feedback and authors' publication stability.

The object of the study is user activity on the Ficbook platform.

The subject of the study is patterns of reader engagement, publication dynamics, and the formation of pseudo-engagement in completed multi-chapter works.

The aim of the study is to identify how the structure of completed maxi works and the character of reader feedback change under conditions of platform instability, and to determine whether a decrease in feedback affects the pace of publication and the completion of large works.

2. Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1. Changes in the structure of feedback after the platform block

The assumption is that after Ficbook was blocked, the main observed change is not so much a direct decrease in the number of completed works as a change in the structure of reader response: the average number of comments and likes decreases, and some categories become less accessible for sampling according to the original criteria.

Expected result: an increase in the number of substitute categories within the sampling matrix, a decrease in median feedback indicators, and greater difficulty in forming a corpus of completed maxi works.

Hypothesis 2. Decline in reader engagement after a certain stage of publication

The assumption is that maximum reader engagement occurs in the early chapters of a work, after which the frequency of comments begins to decline regardless of the overall quality of the work.

Expected result: a stable decrease in average comment density after 25–40% of the total text volume, approximately after chapters 8–10.

Hypothesis 3. The effect of author publication burnout

The assumption is that a decrease in the amount of reader feedback is associated with an increase in intervals between chapter publications and increases the likelihood of publication slowdown or a prolonged completion process.

Expected result: a stable increase in intervals between chapters after a decrease in comment activity.

Additional hypothesis. Pseudo-engagement

A formally high volume of comments does not always indicate a broad reader audience: a substantial part of the activity may be generated by repeated users and by the authors themselves.

Expected result: a high share of repeated commenters and a noticeable share of comments left by the author of the work.

3. Sample and Inclusion Criteria

The study includes 870 completed literary works published on Ficbook.net between January 2021 and February 2026.

Of these:

- 435 works belong to the period before the resource was blocked by Roskomnadzor (up to July 12, 2024);
- 435 works belong to the period after the block (from July 12, 2024 to February 2026).

The difference in the length of the two observed periods is not a matter of researcher preference, but is related to the unequal duration of the observation windows and the “sample maturation” effect: some works started after the block had not yet reached the inclusion criteria at the time of analysis, such as length, completion status, and accumulated feedback.

Each subsample was formed as a stratified quota sample with control for fandom, category/direction, rating, and popularity group.

Inclusion criteria:

- the work is longer than 70 pages, corresponding to the “maxi” class in Ficbook’s classification;
- the work was completed at the time of analysis;
- the text was placed in one of the selected segments: Naruto, BTS, Harry Potter, Marvel, or original works.

If a specific fandom did not contain a sufficient number of relevant completed works, priority was given to preserving the structural parameters of the sample (category/direction, rating, and like group), while missing positions were compensated through fandom substitution. This approach made it possible to preserve category comparability without artificially distorting rare cells of the sample.

3.1. Formation of the Sampling Matrix

To ensure comparability between subsamples, a stratified quota matrix was used. It controlled for three key parameters: category/direction of the work (het, slash, gen), rating (R, NC-17), and level of popularity.

A threshold of 200 likes was used as the operational boundary of popularity. This indicator is not an official metric of the Ficbook platform, but within the user and author communities it functions as an informal marker of a work’s visible success. At the level of platform perception, works that have received 200 or more likes are usually perceived as noticeable and relatively popular, while works with fewer likes more often belong to the less visible segment. In this study, the threshold is used not as an absolute evaluation of textual quality, but as a practical boundary for dividing the corpus into two comparable groups: “200+” and “<200”.

The quota sizes within cells (8, 9, and 10 works) do not reflect the exact statistical share of categories on the platform. Instead, they establish a research balance between the most significant and comparable segments of the sample.

Larger quotas were assigned to categories that form a stable pool of completed maxi works and allow comparative analysis on a sufficient volume of material, for example het, NC-17, and the “200+” group. Minimum quotas were used for less prioritized or auxiliary categories in order to avoid the artificial dominance of individual categories within the overall sample.

If a specific fandom did not contain enough relevant completed works, priority was given to preserving the structural parameters of the sample: category/direction, rating, and like group. Missing positions were compensated through fandom substitution.

The final size of one fandom subsample was 87 works.

3.2. Criteria for Fandom Substitution

The original sampling matrix included works from several large and stable Ficbook segments: Naruto, BTS, Harry Potter, Marvel, and original works. These categories were selected as sufficiently large pools of completed maxi works that made it possible to form a comparable quota sample by category/direction, rating, and like group.

Original works are not treated in this study as a control group and are not opposed to fandom-based works as a separate object of comparison. They are included in the corpus as an independent large segment of the platform, alongside the selected fandoms.

During corpus formation, some cells of the matrix turned out to be insufficiently filled. This was especially true for combinations of fandom, category/direction, rating, and like group where it was not always possible to find the required number of completed maxi works that met all inclusion criteria. In such cases, priority was given to preserving the structural parameters of the sample: category/direction, rating, and popularity group. Fandom was treated as a more flexible variable and could be replaced if the original category did not contain a sufficient number of relevant works.

4. Data Collection and Processing Methodology

4.1. Data Collection

Data were collected from publicly accessible Ficbook pages: work pages, chapter lists, and comment sections. Collection was partially automated using a custom Python script operating through an authorized user’s browser session. Links to works were passed to the script in batches through the file links.txt; one run usually included 15–25 links, because a larger number of requests could trigger Cloudflare restrictions. After each batch was processed, an intermediate dataset file was generated and then incorporated into the overall research table.

4.2. Dataset Structure

The source dataset has a two-level structure. The first level consists of work-level tables, where one row corresponds to one completed work. At this level, the following variables were recorded: work identifier, publication start and end dates, fandom, category/direction, rating, number of likes, length in pages, number of chapters, total number of comments, number of author comments, and the number of unique users who left comments.

The second level consists of chapter-level tables, where one row corresponds to one chapter of a work. At this level, the following variables were recorded: work identifier, chapter number, chapter publication date, and number of comments on the chapter. These data were used to analyze engagement dynamics and publication intervals.

4.3. Data Cleaning and Metric Calculation

Before analysis, the data underwent cleaning and standardization. Numerical indicators were converted to a unified format; publication dates were processed as calendar values; and the popularity group was recalculated automatically based on the number of likes: works with 200 or more likes were assigned to the “200+” group, and works with fewer likes were assigned to the “<200” group. This made it possible to avoid errors related to manual labeling and inconsistent category spelling.

Intervals between chapter publications were calculated not from manually entered values, but from the actual publication dates of chapters: for each work, the difference in days between consecutive chapters was calculated. Negative intervals resulting from changes in chapter order, edited dates, or publication-specific features were excluded from analysis. For the analysis of publication slowdown, zero intervals and intervals longer than 365 days were also excluded as extreme outliers.

When testing the hypothesis of author publication burnout, works whose publication duration was less than 30 days were additionally excluded, because such works do not allow reliable evaluation of slowdown dynamics. A long pause was defined as an interval of 30 days or more between consecutive chapters.

The analysis used descriptive statistics: mean, median, proportions, total values, as well as Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients. Median values were treated as more robust to outliers, especially for likes and comments, where individual highly popular works may substantially shift mean indicators.

4.4. Scraping Limitations

Data collection had a number of technical limitations. Since Ficbook does not provide an open research API, data extraction was performed through browser-based scraping. This approach depends on the current structure of the website pages and may be sensitive to interface changes, dynamic loading of elements, advertising pop-ups, and Cloudflare restrictions.

To increase stability, collection was performed through an authorized browser session, and the number of links in one run was limited to small batches. The script required manual supervision: authorization, correct page loading, and the final data export were checked.

The study relies only on publicly visible indicators: likes, comments, publication dates, text length, and work metadata. Internal platform statistics, including views, completion rates, hidden recommendation algorithms, and actual reach, are not available. Therefore, the results should not be interpreted as full Ficbook statistics; they describe patterns within the constructed corpus of completed maxi works.

5. Research Results

5.1. Changes in the Structure of Feedback After the Platform Block

The data show that after Ficbook was blocked, the corpus of completed maxi works demonstrates a pronounced decrease in reader feedback indicators. At the same time, the structure of the sample by key categories was preserved: in both periods, 435 completed works were analyzed, including 228 works in the “200+” group and 207 works in the “<200” group. The distribution by category/direction also remained the same: 170 het, 90 gen, and 175 slash works in each period. This makes it possible to compare the dynamics of feedback rather than a random shift in sample composition.

The most noticeable change concerns the average level of engagement. The mean number of likes decreased from 848.26 to 499.83, or by approximately 41.07%. The mean number of comments decreased even more sharply: from 346.76 to 186.97, or by approximately 46.08%. Thus, after the block, both major reader feedback indicators decline, with comments falling more strongly than likes.

Median values confirm that the decline concerns not only individual highly popular works that affect the mean, but also the “typical” work in the sample. Median likes decreased from 223 to 211 (approximately 5.38%), while median comments fell from 135 to 79 (approximately 41.48%). The drop in median comments is especially significant: it shows that after the block, not only the overall volume of activity decreased, but also the regularity of reader participation in discussions of works.

A decrease is also observed in the structural characteristics of the works themselves. The mean work length decreased from 249.29 to 219.74 pages (approximately 11.85%); the median length decreased from 166 to 146 pages. The mean number of chapters decreased from 28.93 to 24.76, and the median from 21 to 19 chapters. This may indicate that after the block, more compact works more often enter the corpus of completed maxi works, or that authors find it more difficult to complete longer texts under the previous level of reader feedback.

The changing conditions of corpus formation should also be taken into account separately. Although the final sampling matrix was preserved in comparable volume, the number of substitute fandoms increased substantially after the block. Before the block, the number of works taken outside the original fandom core was 18 out of 435 (4.1%); after the block, this number rose to 89 out of 435 (20.5%). Even under a softer counting procedure, in which alternative spellings of original fandoms are treated as aliases, the number of substitutions after the block is 77 works (17.7%). Thus, the number of substitutions increased by approximately 4.3–5 times, indicating a substantial increase in the difficulty of forming the corpus according to the original criteria.

This result may indicate depletion of the accessible pool of completed maxi works in the specified categories after the block. However, it cannot be interpreted unambiguously as a decrease in author activity alone: the post-block period is shorter, and some authors may have faced technical restrictions on access to the platform and therefore may have been unable to publish regularly. Consequently, the growth in substitutions should be treated as an indicator of reduced accessibility of the relevant corpus rather than as direct evidence that completed works disappeared.

At the same time, it is not possible to speak of the complete disappearance of completed works or of a collapse of all categories. The sampling matrix by category/direction and like group remains filled: both periods include works of different categories and both popularity levels. However, the growth in substitute fandoms, the appearance of a single NC-21 category after the block, and the need for more careful selection indicate not the disappearance of the corpus, but a change in the conditions of its formation: some categories become less stable and less accessible for sampling according to the previous criteria.

Thus, the hypothesis is partially confirmed. The data do not show a direct disappearance of completed maxi works after the block, since the corpus could be formed in comparable volume while preserving the main categories. However, the hypothesis is confirmed in terms of changes in the structure of reader feedback and increased difficulty in sample formation: after the block, the mean indicators of likes and comments decline substantially, the median number of comments falls sharply, and the share of substitute fandoms increases from 4.1% to 20.5%.

A more precise formulation of the result is as follows: after the Ficbook block, completed maxi works continue to appear and remain represented in the main categories, but they receive noticeably less reader feedback, especially in the form of comments. At the same time, the corpus becomes more difficult to assemble according to the original matrix, which may be related both to a reduction in the accessible pool of completed works in the specified categories and to restricted author access to the platform. Therefore, the platform block is associated not so much with the disappearance of completed works as with weakened visible reader engagement and greater difficulty accessing the relevant corpus of works.

5.2. Decline in Reader Engagement After a Certain Stage of Publication

The analysis of comment dynamics by text stage does not confirm the assumption that maximum reader engagement is limited to the early chapters and then followed by a stable decline. On the contrary, the data show a more complex model: engagement remains relatively stable throughout the main body of the work and increases noticeably at the final stage.

In the full sample, the mean number of comments per chapter is 9.93 at the 0–25% stage, 9.69 at the 25–40% stage, 10.84 at the 40–50% stage, and 10.24 at the 50–75% stage. The median at these stages remains close: 4–5 comments. At the final stage, 75–100%, the mean rises to 13.67, while the median is 5 comments. Therefore, the full sample does not show a stable decline in engagement after 25–40% of the text; on the contrary, reader activity increases closer to the completion of the work.

A separate analysis of the periods before and after the block shows a similar distribution pattern. Before the block, the mean number of comments remains almost stable during the first 75% of the text: 12.27 at the 0–25% stage, 12.24 at 25–40%, 13.20 at 40–50%, and 12.27 at 50–75%. The median at all these stages is 6 comments. At the final stage, the mean number of comments rises to 16.16, and the median to 8. After the block, the overall level of comments is lower, but the dynamics remain similar: 7.15 at 0–25%, 6.64 at 25–40%, 7.98 at 40–50%, 7.76 at 50–75%, and 10.65 at 75–100%. The post-block median is 3–4 comments. Thus, the block is associated with a

lower overall level of feedback, but it does not change the basic distribution pattern of engagement across the text.

An additional analysis by popularity group shows that the “200+” group demonstrates a significantly higher level of reader response at all text stages. In the full sample, the mean number of comments for the “200+” group is 14.35 at the 0–25% stage, 14.16 at 25–40%, 16.10 at 40–50%, 15.22 at 50–75%, and 20.64 at 75–100%. The median in this group ranges from 8 to 10 comments and reaches its maximum at the final stage. In the “<200” group, the values are substantially lower: 3.76, 3.40, 3.43, 3.26, and 4.14 comments respectively, with a median of 2 comments at all stages. Therefore, popularity primarily affects the scale of feedback, but it does not cancel the general tendency toward a final-stage increase in activity.

The same pattern holds when the two periods are analyzed separately. Before the block, in the “200+” group, the mean number of comments rises from 17.38 at the initial stage to 24.04 at the final stage, with a median ranging from 10 to 13 comments. In the “<200” group, the indicators are lower and flatter: from 4.73 at the initial stage to 4.99 at the final stage, while the median remains equal to 2. After the block, in the “200+” group, mean values decrease compared with the pre-block period, but the final-stage increase persists: from 10.57 at the 0–25% stage to 16.38 at the 75–100% stage, with a median of 6 at all stages. In the “<200” group after the block, the comment level is minimal: from 2.70 at the initial stage to 3.15 at the final stage, with a median of 1 comment at all stages.

At the work level, the difference between popularity groups is even more pronounced. In the full sample, works in the “200+” group have a mean of 432.30 comments and a median of 245.5, while in the “<200” group the mean number of comments is 84.65 and the median is 41.5. Before the block, the gap is even larger: a mean of 560.99 comments and a median of 371.5 for the “200+” group, compared with 110.80 and a median of 53 for the “<200” group. After the block, indicators decline in both groups: in the “200+” group the mean number of comments is 303.60 and the median is 184; in the “<200” group the mean is 58.50 and the median is 33.

Thus, Hypothesis 2 is not confirmed in its original formulation. The data do not demonstrate a stable decline in reader engagement after 25–40% of the text or after the approximate 8–10 chapter mark. Instead of the model “early peak — subsequent decline,” a different dynamic is observed: relatively stable activity through the main part of the work and a pronounced increase in comments at the final stage. Most likely, final chapters trigger additional audience activation: readers return to the text, react to the completion of the plot, and leave comments more often after the resolution.

At the same time, the hypothesis requires refinement: the popularity of a work substantially affects the volume of reader response, but it does not change the basic shape of its distribution. Works in the “200+” group receive significantly more comments at all stages, but neither this group nor the “<200” group shows the expected stable decline after the early chapters. Therefore, the difference between popular and less popular works lies primarily in the intensity of feedback, not in the direction of its dynamics as the text progresses.

5.3. The Effect of Author Publication Burnout

An analysis of intervals between chapter publications, calculated on the basis of actual chapter publication dates, shows that signs of publication slowdown are indeed present in the sample. However, the data do not allow this effect to be described as a direct and universal relationship between reduced reader feedback and longer publication intervals.

In the full sample, the mean interval between chapters increases consistently as the text progresses. At the 0–25% stage of the work, the mean interval is 6.27 days; at the 25–40% stage, 7.41 days; at the 40–50% stage, 7.98 days; at the 50–75% stage, 9.10 days; and at the final 75–100% stage, it reaches 12.15 days. The median interval also increases, from 3 days at the initial stage to 6 days at the final stage. This indicates an overall slowdown in publication pace closer to the completion of the work.

When the periods before and after the block are analyzed separately, this tendency remains. Before the block, the mean interval between chapters increases from 7.04 days at the 0–25% stage to 13.81 days at the 75–100% stage; the median interval increases from 3 to 7 days. After the block, intervals are generally shorter, but growth is also observed: the mean interval increases from 5.12 days at the initial stage to 9.59 days at the final stage, while the median increases from 3 to 4 days. Therefore, publication slowdown appears in both parts of the corpus, although its absolute values differ.

At the same time, the relationship between reduced reader response and growing publication intervals is limited. In the full sample, 69.74% of works have a higher late-stage mean interval than early-stage mean interval, meaning that most works do demonstrate slowdown in the second part of publication. However, a decrease in comments is recorded for only 37.67% of works. The full pattern corresponding to the stated hypothesis, that is, simultaneous decrease in comments and increase in publication interval, is observed in 24.36% of works. Before the block, this pattern is recorded in 22.25% of works; after the block, in 27.08%. Thus, publication slowdown occurs noticeably more often than its combination with decreased reader activity.

Division by popularity group reveals moderate differences. In the full sample, the publication burnout pattern is observed in 22.75% of works in the “200+” group and 26.50% of works in the “<200” group. Before the block, the difference is more pronounced: 19.42% in the “200+” group versus 25.75% in the “<200” group. After the block, the indicators almost converge: 26.74% for the “200+” group and 27.59% for the “<200” group. This suggests that less popular works somewhat more often demonstrate a combination of declining comments and increasing intervals, although after the block the difference between groups becomes less visible.

The analysis of long pauses between chapters also shows that publication gaps are a significant, but not dominant, part of the dynamics. In the full sample, the share of intervals of 30+ days is 4.57% in the “200+” group and 5.46% in the “<200” group. Pauses of 60+ days occur in 1.81% of intervals in the “200+” group and in 2.19% in the “<200” group. Pauses of 90+ days account for 1.07% and 1.20%, respectively. Thus, long pauses are somewhat more frequent in the “<200” group, but the difference between groups remains moderate.

A separate analysis of the first long pause, defined as a gap of 30 days or more between publications, shows that such pauses occur in a substantial share of works. In the full sample, the first long pause is recorded in 44.74% of works in the “200+” group and 42.07% of works in the “<200” group. In the “200+” group, the return after the first long pause occurs on average at chapter 16.88, with a median of chapter 12, which corresponds to approximately 63.07% of the text. In the “<200” group, the return occurs earlier by chapter number: on average at chapter 11.94, with a median of chapter 10, corresponding to approximately 55.84% of the text. The time from publication start to return after the first long pause also differs: for the “200+” group, the mean value is 163.24 days and the median is 129 days; for the “<200” group, the corresponding values are 122.15 days and 107 days.

After the block, the share of works with a first long pause decreases in both groups: in the “200+” group, from 52.43% to 35.63%; in the “<200” group, from 47.62% to 34.43%. This may indicate not so much a reduction in publication burnout as such, but a change in the composition of the post-block corpus of completed maxi works: works that reach completion are likely more often those with a denser and more stable publication pace.

Correlation analysis also does not confirm a strong direct relationship between declining comments and increasing publication intervals. In the full sample, the Pearson correlation coefficient between change in comments and change in interval is 0.07 for the “200+” group and 0.13 for the “<200” group; the Spearman coefficients are 0.08 and 0.14, respectively. These values indicate a weak relationship and do not allow reduced reader activity to be treated as the main or sufficient factor of publication slowdown.

Thus, the hypothesis is partially confirmed. The data show that as a text progresses, publication intervals increase on average, and long pauses occur in a noticeable share of works. However, reduced reader response is not a universal explanation of this process. Publication burnout should be viewed not as a general law of author behavior, but as one possible scenario appearing in some works and slightly more often associated with less popular works.

A more accurate formulation of the result is as follows: authors do tend to slow down their publication pace in the second half of a work, but this slowdown is only weakly associated with a decrease in comments. Most likely, publication dynamics are determined by a combination of factors: text length, narrative complexity, an author’s individual rhythm, accumulated fatigue, and external circumstances. Reader feedback may be one factor, but it is neither the only nor the determining mechanism of publication slowdown.

5.4. Pseudo-Engagement

The analysis of comment structure confirms that a formally high volume of feedback cannot always be interpreted as an indicator of a broad reader audience. The data show that a substantial share of comments is generated not only by many different readers, but also by repeated activity from a limited circle of users and by replies from the authors themselves.

In the full sample, the mean share of author comments is approximately 29.7%, while the median share is 33.3%. In other words, for a typical work, approximately every third comment in the

feedback section is left by the author. This is a significant indicator, because the total volume of comments in such cases reflects not only external reader activity, but also the dialogic structure of discussion, where the author actively participates in producing visible feedback.

A separate analysis of the periods shows that the share of author comments remains stable both before and after the block. Before the block, the mean share of author comments is 30.5%; after the block, 29.7%. The median value is identical in both periods and equals 33.3%. Therefore, author participation in comments is not a random feature of individual works, but a stable characteristic of the studied corpus.

Indicators of commenter uniqueness also point to the presence of pseudo-engagement. Before the block, the mean share of unique commenters is 28.5%, with a median of 23.8%. After the block, these values increase slightly: the mean reaches 33.7%, and the median reaches 26.3%. However, even after this increase, the median value remains low: in a typical case, the number of unique users is only about one quarter of the total number of comments. This means that a substantial part of discussion is produced by repeated commenters.

This is additionally confirmed by the number of comments per unique commenter. Before the block, the mean value is 6.05 comments per unique user, with a median of 4.19. After the block, the indicators decrease slightly: the mean is 5.13 and the median is 3.80. Thus, after the block, discussions become somewhat less concentrated, but commenter repetition remains: a typical active participant leaves not one comment, but several.

The ratio between unique commenters and likes should also be considered. Before the block, the mean value of this indicator is 0.108; after the block, 0.116. This means that the number of unique participants in comments is substantially smaller than the number of users who liked the work. In other words, a like remains a more mass and “lightweight” action, while commenting is produced by a much narrower and more active part of the audience.

Division by popularity group shows that pseudo-engagement appears in both groups, but in different forms. In the full sample, the median share of author comments in the “200+” group is about 29.0%, while in the “<200” group it is 37.5%. This suggests that in less popular works, author participation has a stronger effect on the visible volume of comments. At the same time, the median share of unique commenters is close in both groups: about 24.2% in the “200+” group and 26.3% in the “<200” group. Therefore, the difference between groups is related not only to audience breadth, but also to the character of author-reader interaction.

Before the block, the difference between groups is especially visible: the median share of author comments is 30.8% in the “200+” group and 36.7% in the “<200” group. After the block, this gap remains: 27.1% in the “200+” group versus 37.7% in the “<200” group. Thus, less popular works consistently demonstrate a stronger dependence of visible feedback on author participation.

Therefore, the additional hypothesis is confirmed. A high number of comments cannot automatically be treated as an indicator of a broad reader audience. Comments in the studied corpus reflect not only the scale of external interest, but also the intensity of interaction between the author and a small group of active readers.

A more precise formulation of the result is as follows: comments on Ficbook are not only a metric of reach, but also a metric of communication density. The same high number of comments may indicate either a broad audience or an active dialogue within a small group of users. Therefore, when assessing reader engagement, the number of comments must be considered together with the share of author replies, the number of unique commenters, and the number of comments per participant. Without these qualifications, the total number of comments may create a pseudo-engagement effect, where visible activity is higher than the real breadth of the audience.

5.5. Additional Findings on Publication Seasonality

The analysis of seasonality shows that publication activity is distributed unevenly, but its profile differs before and after the block.

Before the block, the start of works is distributed relatively evenly across the first half of the year. The highest number of started works occurs in March, with 44 works (10.1%); January, February, and June each have 43 works (9.9%); May has 41 works (9.4%); and April has 40 works (9.2%). The lowest values are observed in October, with 23 works (5.3%), and November, with 26 works (6.0%). Thus, before the block, the start of new completed maxi works more often occurred in the winter-spring and early summer period.

After the block, the structure of starts changes. The highest number of started works occurs in October, with 56 works (12.9%); January and December each have 49 works (11.3%); and February has 44 works (10.1%). The lowest values are recorded in April, with 17 works (3.9%); May, with 20 works (4.6%); and June, with 25 works (5.8%). This may indicate a shift in activity toward the end and beginning of the calendar year, although this result must be interpreted cautiously: the post-block period is shorter, and the corpus itself may have been distorted by restricted access to the platform.

Seasonality of work completion is more pronounced. Before the block, the completion peak occurs in May and June: each month has 63 completed works (14.5%). A high value is also observed in April, with 49 works (11.3%). The minimum occurs in August, with 12 works (2.8%); September, with 19 works (4.4%); and March and October, each with 26 works (6.0%). This may indicate that a substantial share of authors brought works to completion in spring and early summer.

After the block, the maximum number of completions occurs in February, with 96 works (22.1%); December, with 61 works (14.1%); and January, with 55 works (12.7%). Other months are noticeably lower: March has 22, April 21, May and June 24 each, July 23, and August and September 22 each. Thus, after the block, completions are more strongly concentrated in the winter period, especially in February and December.

If one considers not only the start and completion of works, but also chapter publication, before the block the most active month by number of chapters is May, with 1,362 chapters (10.9% of all chapters in the period). It is followed by April (1,170), March (1,167), February (1,127), and January (1,124). At the same time, the highest average feedback per chapter is recorded in June, at 16.89 comments, followed by December (14.86), May (14.58), August (14.36), and April (14.35).

This shows that the maximum number of publications and the maximum number of comments do not fully coincide.

After the block, December leads in the number of published chapters, with 1,432 chapters (13.3%); followed by January, with 1,366 (12.7%); February, with 1,286 (11.9%); and October, with 1,173 (10.9%). At the same time, the highest average number of comments per chapter is observed in August (10.44), June (10.00), March (9.77), and April (8.73). Thus, after the block, the highest publication density is concentrated in winter, but a higher average response per chapter does not necessarily occur in the most publication-heavy months.

Overall, the seasonality can be summarized as follows: before the block, activity is more evenly distributed across the first half of the year, with a spring-summer peak in completions; after the block, starts, chapters, and completions become more concentrated in the winter months and in October–December. However, this conclusion should be treated as descriptive rather than causal: the differences may be related not only to author behavior, but also to the different duration of the compared periods, access restrictions, and the specific selection of completed maxi works.

5.6. Correlation Between Popularity and Number of Pages

The relationship between work popularity and text length is weak.

Before the block, the correlation between number of likes and number of pages is 0.18 by Pearson and 0.28 by Spearman. This indicates a weak positive relationship: longer works may receive somewhat more likes, but the dependence is not strong.

After the block, the relationship almost disappears: the Pearson correlation is -0.03 , and the Spearman correlation is 0.12. In other words, after the block, work length is almost unrelated to the number of likes.

In the full sample, the correlation between likes and pages also remains weak: 0.10 by Pearson and 0.21 by Spearman. Therefore, the data do not support the claim that longer works automatically become more popular. Text length may slightly increase the likelihood of accumulating response under certain conditions, but by itself it is not a reliable predictor of popularity.

A more accurate formulation is that a work's popularity is determined less by the number of pages than by a combination of factors: fandom, category/direction, rating, author audience, publication pace, genre expectations, and visibility on the platform.

5.7. Additional Statistics: Ratio Between Likes and Unique Commenters

An analysis of the ratio between likes and unique commenters shows that comments are produced by a substantially narrower part of the audience than likes. In the full sample, 586,419 likes correspond to 46,377 unique commenters, which amounts to 7.91%. At the level of a typical work, the median share of unique commenters relative to likes is 9.94%. In other words, approximately 8–10% of users who liked a work are represented in the comments, while the majority of the audience limits itself to a lighter form of response: the like.

A separate analysis of the periods shows that after the Ficbook block, absolute indicators decline noticeably: the total number of likes decreases from 368,991 to 217,428, and the number of unique commenters decreases from 28,958 to 17,419. However, the relative share of unique commenters among users who liked works remains stable and even increases slightly: the aggregate indicator rises from 7.85% to 8.01%, and the median value by work rises from 9.62% to 10.17%. This suggests that after the block, the overall scale of the visible audience decreases, but the core of active commenters maintains a comparable relative presence.

The division by popularity groups reveals an important difference between breadth and density of engagement. In the “200+” group, unique commenters account for 7.60% of likes, while in the “<200” group this indicator is higher, at 11.72%. Therefore, less popular works have a smaller audience in absolute numbers, but a relatively higher share of users who move from liking to commenting. In other words, these works have a narrower but denser audience: fewer people, but a larger share of them enter into direct interaction with the text.

This pattern holds within both periods. Before the block, unique commenters accounted for 7.54% of likes in the “200+” group and 12.09% in the “<200” group. After the block, the corresponding values are 7.70% and 11.21%. Thus, popular works consistently receive more response in absolute terms, while less popular works demonstrate a higher relative density of commenting.

Consequently, likes and comments cannot be treated as interchangeable indicators of popularity. Likes reflect a broader and less costly form of response, while comments are produced by a much smaller but more active audience segment. To assess reader engagement, it is important to distinguish the scale of response from the depth of interaction: a work may have many likes but a relatively small share of commenters, while a work with smaller reach may have a denser communicative core.

6. Discussion

The results show that changes in user activity on Ficbook after the block cannot be reduced to a simple decline or disappearance of completed works. A more accurate model is structural reconfiguration: completed maxi works continue to appear, but the corpus becomes more difficult to form according to the previous criteria, and indicators of visible reader response decline noticeably.

The growth in substitute fandoms after the block indicates a decline in the accessibility of the relevant corpus within the original categories. This indicator cannot be interpreted unambiguously as a direct decrease in author activity, because the post-block period is shorter and some works may not yet have had enough time to go through the full cycle of publication and completion. In addition, technical access restrictions may have affected both authors and readers. Nevertheless, the increase in substitutions shows that the previous sampling matrix became less stable after the block.

The distinction between likes and comments is especially important. Likes represent a lighter and more mass form of response, while comments require greater involvement, time, and willingness to enter into communication. Therefore, the stronger decline in comments compared with likes may indicate not only a reduction in audience size, but also weakening of the platform’s dialogic

environment. In other words, after the block, not only the visibility of works is affected, but also the intensity of author-reader interaction.

The results of the analysis of comment dynamics by text stage did not confirm the assumption of an early engagement peak followed by a stable decline. On the contrary, comments remain relatively stable throughout the main body of the work and increase at the final stage. This suggests a possible “finale effect”: readers become more active closer to the completion of the plot, return to a work after chapters have accumulated, or leave comments more often after the resolution. This result is important because it shows that long-form writing on Ficbook does not necessarily lose reader attention by the middle of the text.

The hypothesis of author publication burnout was only partially confirmed. Intervals between publications do increase closer to the end of a work, and long pauses occur in a significant share of works. However, the relationship between declining comments and growing intervals remains weak. This means that publication slowdown cannot be explained solely by a drop in feedback. Most likely, publication pace is influenced by a combination of factors: the difficulty of completing a long text, accumulated fatigue, the author’s individual rhythm, external circumstances, and technical access to the platform.

The phenomenon of pseudo-engagement deserves special attention. Comments are not a pure metric of audience breadth: their volume may be generated by repeated users and by active participation from the author. In this sense, comments reflect not only reach, but also communication density. A high number of comments may indicate either a broad audience or an intensive dialogue within a small group of regular readers. Therefore, when analyzing engagement, comments should be considered together with the number of unique commenters, the share of author replies, and the ratio of comments to likes.

Dividing works into the “200+” and “<200” groups made it possible to demonstrate the difference between the scale and density of reader response. Works in the “200+” group receive more likes and comments in absolute terms, but works in the “<200” group show a higher relative share of unique commenters among users who liked the work. Therefore, less popular works may have a smaller but more communicatively active audience.

Overall, the results show that user activity on Ficbook does not disappear after the block, but changes form. The visible audience contracts; comments, as a more effortful form of response, decline more strongly; the corpus of completed maxi works becomes more difficult to form according to the original criteria; and author publication dynamics are determined not only by feedback, but also by a more complex set of factors. Thus, Ficbook after the block should be considered not as a destroyed digital environment, but as a transforming one.

7. Research Limitations

The study has a number of methodological and technical limitations that must be taken into account when interpreting the results.

1. The sample is stratified and quota-based, not representative of the entire Ficbook platform. The matrix was formed to compare specific categories: category/direction, rating, like group, and

publication period. Therefore, the results describe patterns within the constructed corpus of completed maxi works, but cannot automatically be generalized to the entire body of Ficbook texts, including mini works, midi works, unfinished works, and small fandoms.

2. The compared periods differ in duration. The pre-block period covers a longer time interval, while the post-block period is shorter and closer to the time of data collection. This creates a “sample maturation” effect: some works started after the block may not yet have been completed or accumulated likes, comments, and a stable reader audience. Therefore, the decrease in feedback after the block cannot be interpreted solely as a direct decline in interest in the platform.
3. The Ficbook block may have affected not only reader activity, but also authors’ ability to publish. Restricted access to the site, technical failures, the need for workarounds, and changes in user habits may have reduced both publication frequency and the amount of feedback. Within the framework of this study, it is impossible to fully separate a decrease in audience interest from the technical restriction of access to the platform.
4. The study relies only on publicly visible indicators: likes, comments, publication dates, text length, rating, category/direction, and fandom. Internal platform analytics are unavailable. The dataset contains no data on views, completion rates, bookmarks, recommendation traffic, or algorithmic visibility. Therefore, likes and comments are treated as indicators of visible engagement, not as a complete measure of a work’s real reach.
5. The like indicator has limited interpretability. Since one user can like a given work only once, the number of likes can be treated as the number of unique users who performed this action. However, it is impossible to determine what share of all readers liked the work, because the total number of readers and views is unknown. Therefore, the ratio of unique commenters to likes shows not the percentage of commenters among the whole audience, but only the share of commenters relative to users who left a like.
6. Comments are not a pure indicator of audience breadth. Their number depends not only on the number of readers, but also on the communicative culture of a specific work: the author’s reply activity, the presence of regular commenters, genre expectations, fandom norms, and discussion practices. Therefore, a high volume of comments may reflect either a broad audience or an intensive dialogue within a relatively small group of users.
7. The analysis of publication intervals has limitations related to platform-specific publication practices. Authors may edit chapter order, change dates, publish several chapters in one day, or return to old works after long breaks. To reduce distortions, negative and zero intervals were excluded from the publication slowdown analysis, and intervals longer than 365 days were treated as extreme outliers. Nevertheless, the influence of individual publication strategies cannot be fully eliminated.
8. Fandom substitutions in the formation of the sampling matrix are both a methodological solution and a limitation. They made it possible to preserve balance by category/direction, rating, and like group, but also show that the original fandom categories were not equally available for sampling. The especially noticeable increase in substitutions after the block may indicate depletion of the relevant corpus, but it may also be related to the shorter post-block period and technical access restrictions.

9. The 200-like threshold is used as an operational boundary of popularity based on user norms and practical perception within the Ficbook community, not as an official platform metric. Therefore, the “200+” and “<200” groups should be understood as an analytical division by level of visible response, not as an objective classification of the quality or literary value of a work.

Finally, the study is quantitative and descriptive-analytical in nature. It allows stable patterns in corpus structure, feedback dynamics, and publication intervals to be identified, but it does not establish direct causal relationships. In particular, the decrease in comments after the block, the growth of publication intervals, or the increase in substitute fandoms may be associated with several factors at once. Therefore, the results should be interpreted as empirical indicators of changes in user activity, not as a final explanation of the causes of these changes.

8. Conclusion

The study showed that user activity on Ficbook after the platform block cannot be described through a simple model of direct decline or disappearance of completed works. A more accurate model is structural transformation: completed maxi works continue to appear, but the conditions for forming the relevant corpus, the character of reader feedback, and authors’ publication dynamics change noticeably.

The comparison of subsamples before and after the block showed that, while the matrix remains comparable by category/direction, rating, and popularity group, the main indicators of visible reader response decline after the block. The decrease in comments is especially significant: comments fall more strongly than likes and therefore indicate not only a reduction in overall activity, but also weakening of the dialogic component of the platform. A like remains a lighter and more mass form of response, while a comment requires greater participation and is therefore more sensitive to changes in the platform environment.

At the same time, the study revealed greater difficulty in forming a corpus of completed maxi works according to the original criteria. The growth in substitute fandoms after the block shows that some categories became less accessible for sampling. However, this result cannot be explained unambiguously by a decline in author activity: it may also have been influenced by the shorter duration of the post-block period, the “sample maturation” effect, and technical access restrictions. Therefore, the increase in substitutions should be treated as an indicator of changes in the accessible corpus, not as direct evidence of the disappearance of completed works.

The hypothesis of a decline in reader engagement after the early stage of publication was not confirmed. The data did not show a stable decrease in comments after 25–40% of the text or after the approximate 8–10 chapter mark. On the contrary, engagement remains relatively stable throughout the main body of the work and increases at the final stage. This supports the possibility of a “finale effect”: readers become more active closer to the end of the plot, return to the work after chapters have accumulated, or leave comments more often after the resolution.

The hypothesis of author publication burnout was partially confirmed. Intervals between publications do increase closer to the end of a work, and long pauses occur in a noticeable share of

works. However, the relationship between declining comments and growing intervals is weak. This means that publication slowdown cannot be reduced solely to a drop in feedback. Most likely, publication pace is influenced by a combination of factors: the length and complexity of the text, author fatigue, the author's individual working rhythm, external circumstances, and technical access to the platform.

The additional hypothesis of pseudo-engagement was confirmed. Comments are not a pure indicator of audience breadth: a significant share of them may be produced by repeated users and by replies from the author. Therefore, comments should be viewed not only as a metric of reach, but also as an indicator of communication density. A high number of comments may reflect either a broad audience or intensive dialogue within a small group of regular participants.

Additional findings also showed that work popularity is only weakly related to length: the number of pages is not a reliable predictor of the number of likes. At the same time, the ratio of unique commenters to likes shows that only a small share of users who liked a work move to a more active form of interaction. In the full sample, unique commenters constitute about 8% of the number of likes, confirming the distinction between breadth of response and depth of engagement.

Thus, Ficbook after the block should be viewed not as a destroyed digital environment, but as a transforming one. The visible audience contracts; comments, as a more effortful form of response, become more vulnerable; the corpus of completed maxi works becomes harder to form according to previous criteria; and author publication stability depends not only on feedback, but on a more complex set of factors.

The significance of the study lies in the fact that it offers an empirical way to analyze a fanfiction platform not only as a literary archive, but also as a social environment in which text, author, reader, and platform form a single system of interaction. The results may be useful for further studies of digital amateur literature, platform instability, author motivation, and mechanisms of reader engagement in online communities.

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